

Stepwise Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Cu(II) and Ni(II) Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-5-Chloroacetophenoneanil

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The complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenoneanil (HCAA) have been investigated by the potentiometric titration technique in 60% v/v dioxane-water media at $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO_4). The proton-ligand stability constant and the stepwise formation constants of the complexes have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique. The log K values have been determined by different methods. The overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS at 25°, 30° and 35° have also been evaluated.

THE complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) with (HCAA) have been studied potentiometrically^{1,2}. The present investigation deals with the potentiometric studies on complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenoneanil (HCAA). The composition, stability and thermodynamic parameters like ΔG , ΔH and ΔS in 60% v/v dioxane-water media at $\mu=0.1M$ at 25°, 30° and 35° have been determined.

Experimental

The expanded scale pH meter of systronic with a wide range (0.01 pH) glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode were used for pH measurements.

The potentiometric titration was carried out in dioxane-water 60% v/v media at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$) maintained by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate solutions. The titration was carried out in an inert atmosphere. The metal perchlorate solutions were standardised complexometrically. The dioxane was purified by the method given in Vogel³. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by a standard technique⁴. All chemicals used were of BDH AnalaR grade.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.5 M) keeping the total volume of 40 ml. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in an electrically maintained thermostat having accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

- (i) 0.8 ml (1.062M) HClO_4 + 4.0 ml (1M) NaClO_4 + 11.2 ml water + 24.0 ml dioxane
- (ii) 0.8 ml (1.062M) HClO_4 + 4.0 ml (1M) NaClO_4 + 11.2 ml water + 2.0 ml (0.1M) ligand + 22.0 ml dioxane.

- (iii) 0.8 ml (1.062M) HClO_4 + 4.0 ml (1.0M) NaClO_4 + 10.8 ml water + 2.0 ml (0.1M) ligand + 0.4 ml (0.1M) metal + 22.0 ml dioxane.

The average number of protons associated with HCAA ($\bar{n}_A$), average number of ligands attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$) and free ligand exponent (pL) were calculated using the formulas of Irving and Rossotti⁵.

From the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL formation curves were plotted as in Fig. 1 and the formation constants were determined by the usual computational methods as given in Table No. 1.

Fig. 1: Formation Curves of (A) Cu(HCAA), and (B) Ni(HCAA)₂ at 30°

TABLE--1. STABILITY CONSTANTS OF CU(II) AND NI (II) CHELATES OF 2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROACETOPHENONEANIL

At $\mu=0.1 M$ in 60% v/v dioxane-water media.

Chelate	Temp. °C		Computational methods used				
			A	B	C	D	E
Cu(HCAA) ₂	25	log K ₁	8.52	8.51	8.57	8.56	8.60
		log K ₂	6.62	6.65	6.59	6.61	6.57
		log/β	15.14	15.16	15.16	15.17	15.17
Cu(HCAA) ₂	30	log K ₁	8.38	8.39	8.44	8.44	8.41
		log K ₂	6.47	6.48	6.43	6.45	6.45
		log/β	14.85	14.87	14.87	14.89	14.89
Cu(HCAA) ₂	35	log K ₁	8.20	8.18	8.24	8.25	8.25
		log K ₂	6.38	6.40	6.35	6.34	6.36
		log/β	14.58	14.58	14.59	14.59	14.61
Ni(HCAA) ₂	—	log K ₁	7.31	7.31	7.36	7.34	7.37
		log K ₂	5.51	5.50	5.45	5.45	5.44
		log/β	12.82	12.81	12.81	12.79	12.81
Ni(HCAA) ₂	30	log K ₁	7.21	7.22	7.24	7.25	7.22
		log K ₂	5.34	5.33	5.30	5.30	5.32
		log/β	12.55	12.55	12.54	12.55	12.54
Ni(HCAA) ₂	35	log K ₁	7.03	7.01	7.07	7.06	7.06
		log K ₂	5.28	5.30	5.23	5.25	5.24
		log/β	12.31	12.31	12.30	12.31	12.30
HCAA	25	log P _{K₁} H	—	—	10.82	10.80	10.80
		log P _{K₂} H	—	—	3.60	3.61	3.60
		log/β	—	—	14.42	14.41	14.40
HCAA	30	log P _{K₁} H	—	—	10.77	10.76	10.75
		log P _{K₂} H	—	—	3.56	3.56	3.56
		log/β	—	—	14.33	14.32	14.31
HCAA	35	log P _{K₁} H	—	—	10.73	10.72	10.74
		log P _{K₂} H	—	—	3.53	3.52	3.52
		log/β	—	—	14.26	14.24	12.26

A=Least Square method, B=Correction Term, C=Pointwise Calculation,
D=Linear Plot method, E=Half Integral method.

Results and Discussion

In the ligand it is the phenolic -OH group which takes part in the complex formation and so the number of dissociable protons attached per ligand molecule is equal to one.

In the initial stage of the titration the ligand curve shifted to the left (or above), the acid curve due to the basic property of the tertiary nitrogen (C=N) which accepts a proton from the strongly acid medium.

The formation curve of the ligand extends over a range ($0.4 < \bar{n}_d < 1.9$) indicates the formation of the species HL and H_2^+L i.e., phenolic hydrogen and protonated nitrogen are completely dissociable. $\log P_{K_1}H$ and $\log P_{K_2}H$ belongs to the formation of HL and H_2^+L species respectively.

The pH meter reading B for hydrolysis of Cu(II) and Ni(II) were around 5.3 and 7.5 respectively. The deviation of metal ligand complex titration curves were noticed around pH meter reading 4.0 for Cu^{2+} and 5.0 for Ni^{2+} showing the complexation of metal ion with the ligand. The values of $\bar{n}$ obtained were more than 1.0 suggesting 1:2 complexation.

Thermodynamic Parameters

The values of the changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying the metal ligand complex forming relations have been calculated at 25°, 30° and 35° using the relations.

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\frac{d \log K}{d(1/T)} = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57} \text{ (Equation of an isobaric reaction)}^a$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

they are summarised in Table 2.

It is concluded that with the change in temperature there was no appreciable change in the value of stability constants or which almost remain constant.

The stability constant of Cu(II) complex is higher than that of Ni(II) complex.

TABLE-2. THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) CHELATES OF 2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROACETOPHENONEANIL

$\mu = 0.1M$, Solvent : Dioxane-water 60% (v/v)

ΔH	= -23.20,	ΔS	= -8.60 e.u.
Cu(HCAA) ₂	K. Cal/mole	Cu(HCAA) ₂	
ΔH	= -17.48	ΔS	= -13.99 e.u.
Ni(HCAA) ₂	K. Cal/mole	Ni(HCAA) ₂	
Chelate	Temp. °C.	*log/β	ΔG K. cal/mole
Cu(HCAA) ₂	25	15.14	-20.64
Cu(HCAA) ₂	30	14.85	-20.59
Cu(HCAA) ₂	35	14.58	-20.55
Ni(HCAA) ₂	25	12.82	-17.48
Ni(HCAA) ₂	30	12.55	-17.40
Ni(HCAA) ₂	35	12.31	-17.35

* Obtained from Least Square method.

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